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The Intergroup and Contextual Determinants of Real-World Religious Donations: An Experimental Test in Jerusalem

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ABSTRACT

Religious belief commonly relates to prosocial behavior, yet studies suggest that religious individuals tend to limit their prosociality to ingroup members. In this study, we conducted a door-to-door fundraising field experiment to investigate further religious prosociality and ingroup favoritism in a real-world setting. Our results support the association between religiosity and prosociality, showing that religious individuals (compared to secular individuals) were likelier to donate and display hospitality toward fundraisers. However, we also found evidence of ingroup bias by focusing on the role of religiosity level as a boundary of the religious ingroup among co-religionists. Religious people were more inclined to donate to religious fundraisers than secular fundraisers, despite a shared religious affiliation with both. Furthermore, we explored the implications of religious diversity residential context on this nuanced ingroup bias and suggest that the religious community structure alone may not be sufficient to explain the nuances of religious prosocial behavior.

1 | Introduction

“Charity begins at home” (“Aniyei Ircha Kodmim”), a well-known Talmudic expression, encourages individuals to prioritize aiding those who are closest to them. This expression provides a clear reflection of one of the most paradoxical roles of religion in social behavior as enhancing both prosocial behaviors and ingroup favoritism (Saroglou et al. 2005). Yet, by taking a multidimensional approach to religiosity and conceptualizing religion as a social identity (Ben-Nun Bloom et al. 2015, 2021; Saroglou 2011), we can acknowledge the religious divergence between compassion for ingroup and intolerance toward outgroups is not unique. Supporting this understanding, studies focusing on religious prosocial behavior share the same findings as other ingroup favoritism studies: Religious affiliation promotes helping a religious ingroup member more than an outgroup member

(Saroglou 2005; Xia et al. 2021). However, while most studies have examined religious ingroup bias toward members of different religions, such bias can also be directed toward co-religionists who hold lower levels of religiosity (Jackson and Hunsberger 1999; Lavy et al. 2022), indicating that a more nuanced understanding of religious ingroup is required.

Thus, we suggest that in a growing world of multidimensional religious identities, where one can believe without belonging but also belong without believing or behaving (Galen 2012; Wilkins-Laflamme 2014), we should apply a multidimensional approach not only to religiosity itself but also to religious outgroup identification. In this article, we focus on whether the perceived level of religiosity among fundraisers impacts the prosocial behavior of religious individuals. To answer this, we conducted a real-world field experiment of door-to-door fundraising in Israel in July 2019.

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The experiment manipulated the perceived religiosity level of two female fundraisers by alternating their outfits between religious and secular attire. The nonprofit organization “Paamonim” was chosen as the beneficiary of the fundraising effort due to its religious neutrality, ensuring that the organization did not threaten or support any religious values. In this unique design, prosociality is operationalized through the participants’ direct behavior in their natural environment, thus providing a novel and authentic depiction of the phenomenon.

The experiment was conducted in Jerusalem, a context characterized by a complex and profound conflict between various religious groups and the intrareligious cleavage between the ultra-Orthodox and secular Jewish communities. This dynamic intergroup conflict has resulted in numerous clashes and tensions. Given the salience of this cleavage within Jerusalem, our study aimed to deepen the understanding of the boundaries of religious ingroup social identity, particularly regarding what constitutes the “out-group” for religious individuals within the same religious affiliation. Furthermore, by examining this phenomenon in the context of the Jerusalem conflict, we sought to gain insight into the underlying factors of religious real-world prosocial behavior and ingroup favoritism.

Our experimental findings confirm that religiosity increases prosocial behavior and charity as religious individuals donated more than secular individuals and demonstrated more welcoming behavior toward fundraisers. However, we also show religious ingroup favoritism toward other religious individuals, as religious people were more inclined to donate to religious fundraisers (compared to secular fundraisers). This indicates that religious intergroup favoritism can be identified within the same religious affiliation and in a context that does not challenge religious belief.

Our study then moves beyond the intergroup dynamics between religious and secular individuals to explore how religious community structures influence prosocial behavior. We conduct the door-to-door fundraising experiment in Jerusalem’s religiously homogeneous (predominantly religious Jews) and heterogeneous (comprising a mix of religious and secular Jews) neighborhoods. This approach allows us to examine the effects of neighborhood composition on religious prosociality and ingroup favoritism. Our analysis yielded no significant evidence that diversity had positive or negative implications for religious prosociality or ingroup favoritism. In both neighborhoods, religious individuals demonstrated a similar tendency to donate more to religious fundraisers. However, our study demonstrated a negative trend in the religiously homogeneous neighborhood, with a decreased willingness to open the door to an outgroup stranger. This finding may highlight the important distinction between ingroup love and outgroup hate in diverse environments, emphasizing that although religious diversity may not necessarily create a new “us,” it can reduce initial outgroup hostility. Our study suggests that the influence of religious identity on prosocial behavior might extend beyond the boundaries of communal structures. Our analysis indicates that religiosity, as an individual characteristic, may play a more pivotal role in promoting prosocial behaviors than the communal or social aspects of religious settings. This suggests that the intrinsic values and moral frameworks associated with religious identity could be key drivers of prosocial actions, independent of the communal context. This insight

has significant implications for understanding the fundamental drivers of religious prosociality, hinting at the inherent qualities of religiosity itself as a catalyst for such behaviors, rather than solely the influence of community dynamics.

1.1 | Religious Prosociality

Debates regarding the moral implications of religiosity have dominated social science research from its inception. Central to these discussions is the question of whether religious individuals display more moral behavior, especially in terms of prosocial actions, compared to those who are nonreligious. However, despite over six decades of research, a definitive answer to this question remains elusive (Kelly et al. 2024). On the one hand, prosocial behavior is considered natural to religious belief (Norenzayan and Shariff 2008), while religiosity was associated with increased values related to aiding the disadvantaged, such as compassion (Saroglou et al. 2004) and support for the welfare state (Be’ery and Ben-Nun Bloom 2015). Religiosity was also found to strengthen the will to volunteer (Park and Smith 2000; Taniguchi and Thomas 2011), increase generosity (Ahmed 2009), and generally be one of the best predictors of philanthropy and charitable behavior (Bekkers and Wiepking 2011). On the other hand, studies have also challenged the connection between religiosity and prosocial behavior, repeatedly associating religiosity with antisociality (Jackson and Gray 2019), prejudice (Altemeyer 2009), intolerance (Hall et al. 2009), and xenophobia (Johnson et al. 2010).

Galen (2012) first highlighted methodological concerns within the research examining the intersection of religiosity and prosocial behavior. This viewpoint was echoed by Oviedo (2016), who emphasized the multifaceted nature of this relationship. His review indicated that while some studies point to a positive correlation between religiosity and prosociality, others bring to light various constraints and influencing factors, such as cultural contexts, subtleties in religious beliefs, and individual variations in religious practice and interpretation. Such intricacies discourage broad generalizations of the religiosity–prosociality link and advocate for more thorough analyses of these interactions. Building on this theme, Kelly et al. (2024) in their meta-analysis found a stronger association between religiosity and self-reported prosociality than with directly observed prosocial behavior. They argue for the need for more research rooted in tangible, real-world settings that capture actual religious prosocial activities. Our field experiment may offer new insight into this nuanced debate, providing empirical evidence from a real-world context. Accordingly, our first hypothesis posits that *religious individuals (compared to secular individuals) will demonstrate higher prosocial behavior (H1)*.

1.2 | Ingroup Favoritism in the Context of Co-Religionists

A significant challenge in understanding the relationship between religiosity and prosociality is the tendency for religious prosocial behaviors to be predominantly directed toward ingroup members. This pattern has been consistently observed (Oviedo 2016; Saroglou 2019), leading to arguments that religious

prosociality may not fundamentally differ from typical ingroup favoritism (Galen 2012; Bloom 2012).

Theories of political order and social contracts have long emphasized the importance of some collective identity that utilizes the natural trust and solidarity humans have within close-knit networks and expands it toward new, modern, large communities or nations. From this perspective, ingroup favoritism is considered natural, while group loyalty and assimilation are critical for functioning society and solving complicated coordination problems (Efferson et al. 2008). Indeed, perceived similarity is a key factor for prosocial behavior and perceptions of responsibility for others' welfare (Cialdini et al. 1997; Dovidio 2009). Similarly, perceived dissimilarity may foster conflict and antipathy in an intergroup context (Ben-Nun Bloom et al. 2015; Strabac and Listhaug 2008). For this reason, from a social identity theory point of view (Tajfel 1974), intergroup discrimination is more related to favoring one's ingroup than hostility toward the outgroup (Aboud 2003; Brewer 1999). In other words, as humans prefer their group members long before they dislike outgroup members, ingroup bias and impartiality are grounds for intergroup discrimination. Accordingly, numerous studies have established the connection between shared social identity and offering selective help across circumstances and countries (Balliet et al. 2014; Levine et al. 2005).

Like any other social group membership, religious identifiers tend to exhibit ingroup favoritism. However, in the context of intergroup relations, the effect of religion on social outcomes is thought to depend on which dimensions are more salient in a certain context such as compassionate values and beliefs or social identity. Thus, even though religious belief may increase prosocial behavior (Bekkers and Wiepking 2011), the group identity dimension of religiosity directs such prosociality toward other ingroup members (Ben-Nun Bloom et al. 2015, 2021; Preston and Ritter 2013). Saroglou (2005) named this phenomenon "minimal prosociality," concluding that religious prosociality is mainly limited to ingroup members and usually not extended toward outgroup members or circumstances that threaten religious values. For this reason, most studies examining religious "minimal prosociality" have focused on two types of religious outgroups: those belonging to a different religion and those who violate religious values. For instance, Verkuyten (2016) found that religious outgroups received more negative affective ratings in the context of different religious affiliations. Additionally, Xia et al. (2021) revealed that individuals tend to exhibit greater trust in their religious ingroup members, and that religiosity is positively related to the extent of ingroup favoritism in prosocial behavior. This ingroup bias in trust and reciprocity has also been observed between different religious denominations, as demonstrated by Fitzgerald and Wickwire's (2012) investigation into intergroup dynamics between Baptists and Catholics. Regarding violation of religious values, Goplen and Plant (2015) showed that individuals with strong religious worldviews are more likely to display religious prejudice, such as supporting suppression, avoidance, and aggression toward religious outgroups. This bias is particularly evident toward outgroups whose worldviews are perceived as most different and threatening. Furthermore, Rowatt et al. (2009) demonstrated that general religiousness is associated with selective self-reported intolerance toward individuals whose behavior is perceived to be inconsistent with traditional religious teachings, such as homosexuality.

Still, other studies present a more complex understanding of the religious ingroup. For example, Jackson and Hunsberger (1999) show that religious persons reported more positive attitudes toward other religious believers than nonbelievers, regardless of their religious belonging. Similarly, Harper (2007) has shown that religious individuals hold negative stereotypes about non-religious individuals, and Lavy et al. (2022) identified real-world discrimination between religious and secular groups from the same religion. These findings suggest a contextual view of ingroup within a person's religious affiliation. We expect such a nuanced understanding of religious ingroup is particularly required where differences between co-religionists take center stage, as devout and secular groups (or different cults within a religion) compete for political, economic, or symbolic capital. Thus, in a context where one's devoutness—holding constant the religious affiliation—is a salient identity, we can hypothesize that *religious individuals will demonstrate ingroup bias by helping other religious individuals more than secular co-religionists (H2)*.

1.3 | Religious Community

Underlining our first two hypotheses is the question of why religious individuals might be more inclined toward prosocial behaviors. The first hypothesis contends that religiosity itself, with its evolutionary, cognitive, and social-psychological underpinnings, naturally fosters such behaviors. It posits that the fundamental elements of religiosity, encompassing beliefs and moral values, intrinsically drive individuals toward prosocial actions (see to Oviedo 2016 for a review). For example, Pasek et al. (2020) underscore the positive facets of religious belief by showing that religious believers think God prefers universal moral reasoning over exclusive ingroup loyalty. This notion was further elaborated in their subsequent study (Pasek et al. 2023), which demonstrated that religious priming that invokes thoughts of God can enhance prosociality toward religious outgroups. These insights suggest that religious beliefs cultivate prosociality not only through identity affirmation but also through fostering a broad moral outlook.

On the other hand, our second hypothesis suggests that in religious contexts, prosocial behavior is influenced by community dynamics rather than solely by religious belief (Bloom 2012). This view emphasizes the communal and social facets within religious groups, suggesting that the creation of moral communities, beyond just religious doctrines, is key to enhancing prosocial behavior (Galen 2012). To illustrate, Jackson et al. (1995) found that active participation in church groups predicts charitable actions more accurately than church attendance, highlighting that engagement within religious communities bolsters prosocial behaviors. Similarly, Monsma (2007) supports this by showing that social networks within religious settings significantly influence charitable giving, more so than individual religious beliefs.

Merging the impacts of belief and community, Graham and Haidt (2010) contend that religious communities often congregate around morally significant causes, creating strong moral bonds among members. This fusion of belief and belonging forms an effective framework for nurturing prosocial behavior, as these communities frequently promote interdependence, enhancing

members' willingness to dedicate resources to collective causes. With our focus on defining the "religious ingroup," our study further probes how the strength of these communal bonds might affect prosocial behavior patterns, particularly the ingroup favoritism among co-religionists. This leads to our third hypothesis: If religiosity itself promotes prosociality, we would expect to observe heightened prosocial behavior among religious individuals regardless of whether they reside in religiously homogeneous or religiously heterogeneous neighborhoods. Conversely, if prosocial behavior is primarily driven by the strength of community ties, we would anticipate seeing a decrease in prosocial actions among religious individuals living in less religious environments (heterogeneous neighborhoods) compared to their counterparts in more religiously uniform neighborhoods. This hypothesis explores the interplay between the religious environment and the expression of prosocial behavior, helping to disentangle the influences of religious belief and community bonds on prosocial actions.

This hypothesis also relates to the extensive literature about diversity implications, showing that social diversity negatively affects overall levels of social participation and trust (Dinesen et al. 2020), mainly in heterogeneous residential environments (Dinesen and Sønderskov 2015), and lower solidarity and prosocial behavior (Zhang et al. 2019). Moreover, such findings are not limited to intergroup relations only, following Putnam's (2007) constrict theory, which posits that residents of ethnically diverse communities exhibit higher levels of distrust toward members of other ethnic groups and their ingroup and strangers in general. This was also established in Koopmans and Veit's (2014) field experiment, which concluded that ingroup favoritism alone could not explain the decrease in social cooperation within heterogeneous neighborhoods. Thus, in the context of our study, we hypothesize that *religiously diverse residential settings may lead to a general reduction in prosocial behavior (H3)*.

1.4 | Study Setting: The Secular–Religious Intergroup Context in Jerusalem

Jerusalem is renowned for its religious diversity, with Jews, Muslims, Christians, and other religions residing within its borders. According to the Jerusalem Institute for Policy Research (2022a), the city's religious makeup is 59.9% Jewish, 37.2% Muslim, and 2.8% Christian and other religions. However, Jerusalem's religious diversity exists between and within the various religions. Most notably, the intra-Jewish religious cleavage is profoundly evident within Jerusalem. In Israel, the Jewish religious spectrum ranges from secular to ultra-Orthodox, with traditional and Orthodox Jews situated between the two poles (Ben-Porat et al. 2008). The intrareligious divide within Judaism primarily exists between the ultra-Orthodox and more secular Jewish communities. This division is particularly pronounced in Jerusalem, where both groups have sizable populations and are often in conflict. According to the Jerusalem Institute for Policy Research (2022b), 35.4% of Jewish adults in Jerusalem in 2020 were ultra-Orthodox, 20.9% were religious, 10.6% were traditional-religious, 14.2% were traditional-not religious, 18.9% were secular. Notably, the proportion of the ultra-Orthodox community in Jerusalem is three times higher than in the rest of Israel. At the same time, the nonreligious constitute almost twice the

percentage of the Jewish population outside of Jerusalem. The ultra-Orthodox Jewish community in Jerusalem is characterized by its strict adherence to religious tradition and its emphasis on separation from mainstream society. This community is often associated with the Haredi movement, which aims to create a self-sufficient religious community separate from secular society. Ultra-Orthodox Jews in Jerusalem are known for their distinctive dress, strict observance of religious laws, and concentration in specific neighborhoods, such as Mea She'arim.

On the other hand, Jerusalem's more secular Jewish community tends to focus less on religious practice and more on political and social issues. This community is often associated with the Zionist movement and sees Jerusalem as the capital of the Jewish state. The secular community in Jerusalem is more diverse and includes a range of political and religious views but generally supports a more liberal and open approach to religion and society. The intrareligious cleavage between Jerusalem's ultra-Orthodox and secular Jewish communities has led to numerous conflicts, including clashes over public spaces, education, and political representation. The ultra-Orthodox community often seeks to impose its religious practices on the wider community, while the secular community resists such efforts and seeks to maintain a more pluralistic society. The cleavage is also expressed by a large negative immigration of nonreligious people from the city. At the same time, more religious communities (especially ultra-Orthodox) moved into diverse or what were considered more secular neighborhoods. These neighborhoods become more religiously homogeneous, and the others become more diverse (not entirely secular). The prominence of the cleavage in Jerusalem and its unique geographical and residential patterns make it an interesting case for examining our research question.

2 | Method

2.1 | Research Design

Two female experimenters conducted door-to-door fundraising for the real "Paamonim" ("Bells") organization, which is a nonprofit organization operating in Israel that aims to assist families in financial difficulty by providing financial education.¹ The organization was chosen since it is considered religiously neutral and therefore does not threaten or support specific religious values.² In addition, the organization did not conduct door-to-door fundraising in the researched area in recent years. The "Paamonim" organization provided the research team with formal receipts and received all the funds raised during the experiment. The university IRB committee approved the research.

During the door-to-door fundraising activities, the two fundraisers alternated between wearing religious and secular attire. This approach was designed to investigate whether their perceived level of religiosity influenced the likelihood of receiving donations and impacted how they were treated. In Judaism, external attire often signals religious adherence. Typically, religious males might wear yarmulkes and Tzitzit, and the females wear head-dresses, skirts, and long-sleeve dresses. In our experiment, the "religious" outfit included knee-length black skirts and closed

shirts in neutral colors such as green or burgundy with 3/4 length sleeves. In contrast, the “secular” attire consisted of jeans or black pants paired with short-sleeved shirts in green or gray. Therefore, the religious attire of the fundraisers functioned as the primary treatment variable in this experiment. Due to the unique design of the experiment, which did not allow for direct testing of our manipulation on the actual participants, we validated our approach by presenting images of our “religious” and “secular” fundraisers to an additional group of 80 individuals, including residents from the experiment neighborhoods and others from various parts of Jerusalem. Within this test, 91% accurately identified the “religious” fundraisers as religious, and 76% recognized the “secular” fundraisers as secular. These results underscore the effectiveness of our attire-based manipulation in signifying perceived religiosity and its potential influence on social interactions within the fundraising context.

Given our intention to investigate religious diversity implications, we conducted the fundraising experiment on two neighborhoods that differ in their religious homogeneity/heterogeneity level: Givat Mordechai (religiously homogeneous) and Kiryat Hayovel (religiously heterogeneous). The religious diversity level of the neighborhood was set according to data on demographic distribution by schools—that is, to which schools the parents choose to send their children.³ In Givat Mordechai, our homogeneous neighborhood, only 6% of the children go to state-secular schools, 52% to state-religious schools, and 42% to ultra-Orthodox schools.⁴ In other words, most of the children in this neighborhood receive religious-Jewish education. In contrast, in Kiryat Hayovel, our heterogeneous neighborhood, 42% of the children attend state-secular schools, 13% attend state-religious schools, and 45% attend ultra-Orthodox schools.⁵ This suggests a greater diversity in the level of Jewish religiosity.

In addition, Kiryat Hayovel was selected for our study owing to its distinctive demographic transformation. Originally a secular neighborhood, it has become increasingly attractive to religious and ultra-religious families, mainly from more homogeneous areas like Givat Mordechai. The primary lure of Kiryat Hayovel has been its affordability.⁶ Despite similar levels of religious practice in both Kiryat Hayovel and Givat Mordechai, this migration indicates a potential openness among these families to live in a more diverse environment. While economic factors usually outweigh ingroup preferences in residential choices (Bobo and Zubrinsky 1996), this inclination toward openness may still impact the patterns of religious favoritism behavior. It implies that, despite similar religiosity levels, there’s a subtle shift toward embracing a more mixed community, potentially influencing how religious favoritism is expressed within these neighborhoods. It is important to note that we do not test the direction of this impact; hence, it remains uncertain whether these changes are a consequence of the diverse environment itself or pre-existing inclinations toward openness among these families.

Within these neighborhoods, fundraisers knocked on doors across a total of 22 preselected buildings, chosen to be as similar as possible in terms of real-estate measures (based on Madlan Reports, the leading real estate website in Israel), number of apartments per building, and architectural style. Fundraising activities were conducted on six separate days over 2 weeks (on

consecutive Mondays, Wednesdays, and Thursdays in July 2019), alternating the neighborhood sampled each day and varying fundraisers’ attire every two buildings. To achieve an approximately equal number of door openings across neighborhoods, fundraisers continued knocking on doors until reaching a target of about 120 opened doors per neighborhood. Due to variations in residents’ responsiveness, this approach required knocking on 264 doors in the heterogeneous neighborhood and 326 doors in the homogeneous neighborhood. This variance in total doors knocked reflects differences in door-opening rates between neighborhoods, while the preselection of buildings preserved comparability across areas. This point is particularly important, as we recognize that the door-opening rate is not random and is significantly affected by our manipulation, a matter we will elaborate on shortly.

Participants who opened their doors heard a brief description of the “Paamonim” organization and its goals, and were asked to donate any amount they wished. Donors were provided with formal receipts for their contributions, and all door openers were thanked according to a standardized protocol. Throughout the procedure, fundraisers knocked on 590 doors, resulting in 240 opened doors, with 103 participants donating a total of 1322 ILS (approximately 380 USD).

2.1.1 | Measuring Prosocial Behavior

Prosocial behavior includes financial contributions as well as the social interactions that accompany them. This perspective is reinforced by research in fundraising field experiments. For example, DellaVigna et al. (2012) found that social pressure and the discomfort of refusal are significant motivators for donations, often prompting households to avoid door-to-door fundraisers. Similarly, Andreoni et al. (2017) demonstrated that individuals frequently evade fundraisers to avoid the empathic stress and guilt associated with declining to donate. Building on this understanding, our study examined two dimensions of prosocial behavior: first, participants’ monetary donations, capturing both the decision to donate and the amount contributed; and second, their engagement and responsiveness, assessed by the number of doors opened within each building and the level of hospitality shown toward the fundraisers. While donations reveal participants’ financial contributions, these additional measures of engagement and responsiveness provide a richer perspective on prosociality by capturing both their willingness to interact and the quality of their social engagement.

Donation Assessment: We started by differentiating between donors and nondonors using a basic binary measure. A significant challenge in analyzing donation levels stems from the substantial proportion of participants (57.08%) who did not donate at all, combined with the wide range of donations from those who did (ranging from 0.5 to 100 NIS). This scenario, involving high nondonation rates and varied donation amounts, presents difficulties in creating a continuous variable for donation amounts. To address this, we organized donations into five distinct groups, each representing a specific range of monetary contributions: nondonors (0 NIS) in category 1, low donors (1–5 NIS) in category 2, average donors (6–10 NIS) in category 3, generous donors (11–20 NIS) in category 4, and very generous donors (25–100 NIS) in category 5.

Hospitality Assessment: The fundraisers evaluated the participants' hospitality level, discerning genuine willingness to donate from a sense of obligation or social pressure. This subjective assessment used a scale from 1 (not welcoming at all) to 5 (very welcoming). The decision to utilize a five-category ordinal variable was deliberate, aiming to reduce potential reliability issues that could stem from the fundraisers' challenge in differentiating between more subtly graded responses.

Door-Opening Assessment: We used a simple binary metric to track whether participants opened the door for our fundraisers. This measure aimed to assess residents' initial willingness to engage with fundraisers, potentially indicative of prosocial behavior. Recognizing the limitation that we cannot accurately distinguish between doors not opened due to absence or a lack of prosocial inclination, we gathered supplementary postexperiment data for context. We revisited eight buildings (from the original 22) in both neighborhoods to check for signs of occupancy, such as lights being on, during the experiment hours in the afternoon. Our findings indicated that around 46% of residences in the heterogeneous neighborhood and 62% in the homogeneous neighborhood were likely occupied at the time of the experiment.⁷ This additional postexperiment data provide a contextual backdrop, helping to interpret the door-opening behavior recorded during our experiment.

2.1.2 | Control Measures

Due to the unique nature of our experiment, it was not possible to gather self-reported variables from participants. Thus, in addition to the treatment and neighborhood homogeneity or heterogeneity (which function as explanatory variables), our fundraisers gathered supplementary data about the individuals who opened their doors and about the buildings surveyed. This was accomplished using a standardized coding sheet (see Table 1 for descriptive statistics of all variables). A key variable for our study was the participants' level of religiosity. Given the importance of religious levels and types in influencing prosocial behavior, but also considering the self-reported nature of data collection, we recorded this variable in a binary format (1 = religious, 0 = secular) to minimize measurement errors. To validate this method, we presented real-world images of residents from each neighborhood (four from each, including a secular male and female, and a religious male and female) to 50 participants, asking them to classify each person as religious or secular. The results showed a high accuracy rate for correct classification across all eight images, with an average of 7.64, a median and mode of 8, and a standard deviation of 0.5. This confirms the effectiveness of accurately identifying religious status in our study context.

In addition to religious level, our data collection also included the perceived age of the participants, ranging from 18 to 84 years, and their gender (man or woman).⁸ Furthermore, we assessed the socioeconomic status of residents in each building, based on the fundraisers' evaluations of both the outdoor and indoor appearances of the building's environment. To keep socioeconomic status constant, we presampled streets within the two neighborhoods that were matched on their real estate values based on the "Madlan" data and sampled buildings within each street based on the type of building (choosing build-

ings of equivalent size and construction type between the two neighborhood).

2.2 | Analytic Strategy

Due to the uncertainty about the identity and intentions of the participants behind the doors, we could not employ the same analysis regarding our three prosocial behavior variables. Therefore, we present a two-step analysis strategy for the various outcome variables.

For door openers only ($N = 240$), whose religious identity is known, we employed a series of logistic and ordered logistic regressions. Specifically, a logistic binomial regression was conducted on donation status (donated vs. not donated), and an ordered logistic regression was used for hospitality levels and categorized donation amounts. We chose this method because both variables are clearly ordered with only five categories, and their distribution is abnormal.

In the first model for each outcome variable, we checked the main effects of the treatment (the fundraisers' religiosity), and the participants' religiosity. These models aimed to test H1 (religious tend to be more prosocial than seculars). In the second model, we added the neighborhood type for testing H1 and H3 (that religiously heterogeneous neighborhood decreases prosocial behavior) controlling for other variables: the participants' perceived age, gender, and socioeconomic status. In the third model, we tested the interaction between participant religiosity and fundraiser religiosity to examine whether religious participants tend to donate more or exhibit greater hospitality toward co-religionist fundraisers than secular fundraisers (H2). In these models, we employed a detailed by-group analysis to enrich our assessment of the differences created by the four groups created by the interaction: religious individuals exposed to religious fundraisers, religious individuals exposed to secular fundraisers, secular individuals exposed to religious fundraisers, and secular individuals exposed to secular fundraisers.

We then turn to analyze the door-opening variable using an intended-to-treat analytical approach. Incorporating the intended-to-treat analytical approach in analyzing the door-opening variable is particularly advantageous for our study design. This methodology involves considering all 590 door-knocking attempts—both opened and not opened—as part of our observational data set. This approach is pivotal because it accounts for the inherent uncertainties in our experimental setup; specifically, it addresses the challenge of not knowing whether a door wasn't opened due to the resident decision based on the fundraiser's identity or simply because the resident was not home at the time. By including all attempted interactions, we ensure that our analysis remains comprehensive and unbiased, reflecting the full range of possible responses to our fundraisers. This methodological choice aligns with best practices in field experiments for maintaining robustness and reliability, as evidenced in the works of renowned researchers like Gerber and Green (2012), and mirrors the approach used in DellaVigna et al.'s (2012) similar study.

To analyze this variable, we lean on the only known information: the fundraisers' religiosity, the neighborhood, and the socioeco-

TABLE 1 | Descriptive statistics.

	Stats/values	Frequencies (% of valid)	N	Graph
Donation level (DV)	1. Did not donate	137 (57.08%)	240	
	2. Low donation	28 (20%)		
	3. Average donation	45 (32.14%)		
	4. Generous donation	23 (16.43%)		
	5. Very Generous donation	7 (5%)		
Hospitality level (DV)	1. Not nice at all	38 (15.83%)	240	
	2. Below average	29 (12.08%)		
	3. Average	43 (17.92%)		
	4. Nice	62 (25.83%)		
	5. Very nice	68 (28.33%)		
Doors opened (DV)	Opened	240 (40.68%)	590	
	Not opened	350 (59.32%)		
Fundraiser's religiosity (treatment)	Religious	120 (50%)	240	
	Secular	120 (50%)		
Neighborhood	Heterogeneous	121 (50.42%)	240	
	Homogeneous	119 (49.58%)		
Religiosity	Religious	125 (52.08%)	240	
	Secular	115 (47.92%)		
Gender	Women	154 (64.17%)	240	
	Men	86 (35.83%)		
Perceived age	Mean (SD): 47.39 (17.67)	27 distinct values	240	
	Min < Med < Max			
	18 < 45 < 85			
Socio-economic status	1. Very poor environment	0 (0%)	240	
	2. Poor environment	36 (15%)		
	3. Average environment	117 (48.75%)		
	4. Rich environment	19 (7.92%)		
	5. Very rich environment	68 (28.33%)		

omic status of the building. We employed a series of two binomial logistic regressions. The first model aims to test H3, which posits that a religiously heterogeneous neighborhood decreases prosocial behavior. In the second model, we examined the interaction between neighborhood type and fundraiser religiosity. This helped us understand whether the fundraiser's religiosity had a different effect in each neighborhood. Like the third model in the previous outcome variables, we conducted a detailed, per-group analysis of the four groups created by the interaction: doors knocked on in the heterogeneous neighborhood by religious fundraisers, doors knocked on in the heterogeneous neighborhood by secular fundraisers, doors knocked on in the homogeneous neighborhood by secular fundraisers, and doors knocked on in the homogeneous neighborhood by religious fundraisers.

3 | Results

3.1 | Are Religious People More Prosocial?

In our study, we employed logistic regression to examine the main effects of participant religiosity on the likelihood of donating. Models 1 and 2 were developed for this purpose, with Model 1 focusing exclusively on the role of religiosity, while Model 2 integrated additional control variables (Table 2 present's the full logistic regression models). The outcomes from both models consistently demonstrate that religious individuals are significantly more likely to donate than their secular counterparts (odds ratio [OR]: 2.24, 95% confidence interval [CI] [1.33–3.82]; OR: 2.15, 95% CI [1.21–3.86]), regardless of the fundraisers' perceived religiosity

TABLE 2 | Logistic regression analysis on the binary variable of donation. Model 1 examines the main effects of religiosity and treatment, Model 2 includes these main effects with additional control variables, and Model 3 delves into the interaction effects by group, offering insights into how various combinations of participant religiosity and fundraiser religiosity influence donation behavior.

Logistic regression on donating (Donated = 1)									
Predictors	Model 1			Model 2			Model 3		
	Odds ratios	CI	p	Odds ratios	CI	p	Odds ratios	CI	p
Donors' Religiosity [Religious = 1]	2.24	1.33–3.82	0.003	2.15	1.21–3.86	0.009			
Fundraiser's Religiosity [Secular = 1]	0.79	0.46–1.33	0.372	0.76	0.44–1.31	0.326			
Secular donor exposed to secular fundraisers [Reference = religious exposed to religious]							0.36	0.16–0.79	0.012
Religious donor exposed to secular fundraisers [Reference = religious exposed to religious]							0.53	0.25–1.10	0.090
Secular donor exposed to religious fundraisers [Reference = religious exposed to religious]							0.30	0.13–0.68	0.005
Neighborhood [Homogeneous = 1]				1.20	0.69–2.08	0.524	1.09	0.62–1.92	0.759
Age				1.00	0.98–1.01	0.850	1.00	0.98–1.01	0.877
Gender [Men=1]				1.76	1.01–3.08	0.047	1.78	1.02–3.12	0.044
Socio economic				1.07	0.82–1.40	0.613	1.06	0.81–1.39	0.651
(Intercept)	0.55	0.35–0.85	0.010	0.36	0.09–1.37	0.137	1.01	0.24–4.20	0.994
Observations		240			240			240	
R ² Tjur		0.040			0.037			0.039	
Deviance		318.219			313.046			310.926	
AIC		324.219			347.764			347.428	
log-likelihood		–159.109			–156.523			–155.463	

levels. These results suggest that religious participants are two times more likely to donate than secular participants, as seen in Figure 1.

Similarly, our analysis using ordinal logistic regression, which examines the levels of donation amounts, reveals that religious individuals are significantly more likely to donate higher amounts (OR: 1.89, 95% CI [1.15–3.14]; OR: 1.91, 95% CI [1.10–3.36]). Full

models can be found in the online appendix 1. These findings support H1 and the notion that religious individuals are more prone to prosocial behavior.⁹

Further analysis from Model 2, which includes control variables, reveals a distinct gender-based difference in donation behavior. Men were significantly more likely to donate, with an increase of 76%–78% in the odds of donating compared to women (OR:

FIGURE 1 | Main effects of participant religiosity on the likelihood of making a donation using a logistic regression.

1.76/1.78, 95% CI [1.02–3.12]). This gender effect was consistent throughout our analysis for both donation and hospitality.

In our study, we also evaluated the impact of participant religiosity on levels of hospitality. The results from these models suggest a significant effect of religiosity on enhancing hospitality. Specifically, religious participants showed an increased likelihood of higher hospitality levels compared to secular participants. The ORs for this effect are 2.85 with a 95% CI of [1.79–4.58], and 2.37 with a 95% CI of [1.44–3.92], respectively (see the online appendix 1 for full models). These findings further support our first hypothesis, indicating that religiosity positively influences not just the likelihood of donating but also the extent of hospitality offered to fundraisers.

3.2 | Are Religious People More Prosocial Toward Other Religious People?

To examine the presence of ingroup bias among religious participants, we introduced an interaction term between participant religiosity and fundraiser religiosity. This approach enabled us to assess whether exposure to fundraisers of differing religiosity influenced donation propensity among religious participants. The model yielded an insignificant interaction effect. However, given that both variables (participant religiosity and fundraiser religiosity) are categorically binary, we conducted a cell-means analysis to obtain the expected logits for each group created by the interaction: religious participants exposed to a secular fundraiser, religious participants exposed to a religious fundraiser, secular participants exposed to a secular fundraiser, and secular participants exposed to a religious fundraiser. In our H2, we expected to see that for religious participants, the exposure to religious fundraisers would increase the propensity to donate. A closer

examination within the experimental groups, as seen in Figure 2, illustrates this expectation in our models. In Model 3, we see that for religious individuals who were exposed to secular fundraisers, the odds of donating decreased by 47% compared to religious individuals who were exposed to religious fundraisers (OR for this subgroup is 0.53 with a 95% CI of [0.25–1.10]).

Interestingly, in an additional model (presented in the online appendix 1) with secular individuals exposed to secular fundraisers as the reference group, the coefficient for secular individuals approached by religious fundraisers was found to be insignificant. This indicates no difference in donation propensity between secular individuals approached by secular fundraisers and those approached by religious fundraisers (OR for this subgroup = 0.84, 95% CI [0.37–1.90]). Thus, in contrast to the religious ingroup effect, we did not observe a similar secular ingroup effect among secular individuals.

These findings suggest that the fundraiser's perceived religiosity does influence the likelihood of donating, with notable variations across different donor and fundraiser religiosity combinations. Our ordinal logistic regression model examining levels of donation reveals similar patterns to those found in the logistic regression analysis (full models and illustrations can be found in the online appendix 1). This trend was also found in the hospitality assessment, where religious individuals were approached by secular fundraisers, there was a 49% reduction in the odds of displaying greater hospitality, but this finding was significant only at the 90% confidence level. The corresponding OR for this scenario is 0.51 with a 95% CI of [0.26–0.99].

These results, illustrated in Figure 3, highlight the complexities of how a fundraiser's religiosity influences the hospitality extended by individuals. In the left column of the figure, we

FIGURE 2 | Variations among different interaction combinations: Donation. [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

FIGURE 3 | Variations among different interaction combinations: Hospitality. [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

observe that, for religious individuals, changes in the fundraiser's religiosity significantly impact the level of hospitality extended. In contrast, in the right column, representing secular individuals, the fundraiser's religiosity has a minimal effect on hospitality levels.¹⁰

Thus, our findings support H2, highlighting ingroup favoritism rooted in religiosity levels. This bias, as demonstrated, is strongly linked to religious identity, with marked differences observed when religious individuals interact with secular versus religious fundraisers. The significant variance in behavior based on the alignment of individuals and fundraiser religious identities reinforces the influence of religious ingroup favoritism on prosocial actions.

3.3 | Religious Communities and Prosocial Behavior

Our analysis reveals that the diversity of the neighborhood—whether homogeneous or heterogeneous—does not significantly affect prosocial behaviors, including both donation decisions (whether to donate and the amount donated) and hospitality levels. This finding indicates no noticeable difference in prosocial behavior between the heterogeneous and homogeneous neighborhoods, thereby not supporting our third hypothesis. Moreover, in contrast with our third hypothesis, our analysis shows a higher rate of door opening in the heterogeneous neighborhood compared to the homogeneous neighborhood. The main effects logistic regression model reveals that residing in a heterogeneous neighborhood increases the odds of opening the door by 47% relative to a homogeneous neighborhood (OR: 1.47, 95% CI [1.05–2.05]). Additionally, encountering religious fundraisers raises the odds of door opening by 41% compared to secular fundraisers (OR: 1.41, 95% CI [1.00–1.99]). Furthermore, a one-unit increase in the socioeconomic status of the building corresponds to a 19% increase in the likelihood of opening the door (OR: 1.19, 95% CI [1.01–1.40]).

To test whether the fundraisers' religiosity had different effects in each of the neighborhoods, we included the interaction between neighborhood type and fundraisers' religiosity. The general interaction term was insignificant, meaning that we cannot demonstrate general differences between the neighborhoods in the effect of fundraisers' religiosity. However, we can examine the differences between the groups created by the interaction. Figure 4 demonstrates this effect. We noticed that in a homogeneous neighborhood, being approached by secular-outfitted fundraisers led to 37% decrease in the odds of opening the door compared to religious fundraisers in the same neighborhood setting (OR: 0.63, 95% CI [0.40–1.00]). However, in the heterogeneous neighborhood, being approached by secular-outfitted fundraisers did not lead to a significant difference in the propensity of opening the door compared to religious fundraisers in the same neighborhood (OR: 1.21, 95% CI [0.71–2.06]).¹¹

Interestingly, when focusing solely on the religious sample and examining the interaction between neighborhood types and fundraiser appearances, we do not observe a significant interaction. This suggests that there are no notable differences in how religious individuals donate more to those they perceive

as secular in a heterogeneous neighborhood compared to a homogeneous one. The same holds true for our hospitality measures. Therefore, we find no evidence of enhanced ingroup favoritism in the homogeneous neighborhood (full models are available in the online appendix 1).

In conclusion, our findings suggest that the presence of a religious community does not necessarily enhance prosocial behavior, not even toward the religious ingroup. Instead, it appears to increase outgroup hostility, indicating a more complex relationship between religiosity, community structures, and prosocial tendencies. This conclusion prompts a reevaluation of the role of religious communities in shaping social behaviors, especially in the context of intergroup dynamics.

4 | Discussion

Drawing on data from a door-to-door fundraising field experiment that measured real-world behavior, we found a robust association between religiosity and prosociality. In our study, religious people (compared to secular individuals) were significantly more likely to donate money and display hospitality to fundraisers. However, we also provided substantial evidence that this behavior is influenced by ingroup favoritism since religious people were more inclined to donate to other religious fundraisers and displayed more welcoming behavior toward them. In the context of our study, this religious intergroup discrimination was applied within two groups from the same religious affiliation (Jewish) and in a context that does not challenge religious values (charity to a “religiously neutral” organization). Thus, our finding suggests that religious ingroup identification is multilayered and might be influenced by the religious context. Due to the high religious homogeneity in Israel, we believe that in our study, the religious versus secular identity was the most accessible; therefore, the ingroup identification was based on observed religiosity levels. However, we did not examine context implications directly, and the question of how different contexts may change the religious ingroup identification remains open.

This relates to another limitation of our study: the binary approach used to measure the religiosity of our participants. While this was necessary for operational simplicity, it overlooks the diverse spectrum of religious beliefs and practices. This limitation is especially pertinent considering the varied nature of religious orientations that influence prosocial behavior differently (Mikani et al. 2022). It is important to note, however, that compared to mere affiliation, most aspects of religiosity correlate more strongly with prosociality (Kelly et al. 2024). Therefore, the effects we observed might be stronger than what we have marked, not weaker. Future studies might benefit from a more nuanced measurement of religiosity, potentially capturing these subtle yet significant differences. Added to this is the setting of our study, which is set within a specific Jewish context and might not fully encapsulate the diversity of religious practices and beliefs globally. Different religious traditions and sects vary in their emphasis on sociality and moral norms, which could affect the generalizability of our findings (Oviedo 2016). Acknowledging this limitation is crucial, as it underscores the need for caution in extrapolating our results to other religious contexts. Additionally, our study's sample size of 240 cases, while sufficient for reaching

FIGURE 4 | Variations among different interaction combinations: Doors opened. [Color figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/jsr.12961)]

significant outcomes, is relatively limited, potentially affecting the study's broader applicability. Nonetheless, the fact that significant results were obtained despite this constraint underscores the study's robustness. Future research with larger and more diverse samples would be valuable in expanding the generalizability of our findings.

Our study also encounters a methodological limitation in the assessment of hospitality due to the fundraisers' awareness of both the participants' donation behaviors and the condition to which they were assigned (i.e., whether they were wearing religious or secular attire during the interaction). This awareness may have introduced a potential bias in the fundraisers' evaluation of hospitality, impacting the objectivity of this measure.¹² This limitation highlights the need for future research to employ more objective methodologies in assessing subjective variables accurately. Nevertheless, considering the robust real-world measure of donation used in our study and the consistent direction of the hospitality analysis, this variable can be seen as an additional validation of our findings, rather than a standalone outcome. Our study acknowledges another potential bias linked to perceptions of religious individuals as more trustworthy (Hall et al. 2015) and atheists as less so (Edgell et al. 2006; Gervais et al. 2011). While this might have influenced our door-opening results (where the main effect of the treatment was significant), we observed no significant main effect of fundraiser appearance on donations in models accounting for participant identity. This suggests that perceptions of trustworthiness may impact initial interactions but do not consistently affect donation behavior. We take this issue as a general opportunity to address the limitations of our door opening measure. The metric, designed to assess residents' willingness to engage with fundraisers, encounters the inherent limitation of not being able to definitively distinguish between absence and a conscious decision not to open the door. This uncertainty poses a

challenge in accurately interpreting the level of prosocial behavior or its absence. Future research endeavors should consider exploring alternative methodologies that can more accurately differentiate between these two scenarios, thereby enhancing the precision and reliability of similar studies in assessing prosocial behavior. Yet, despite the study's limitations, we can conclude that a more nuanced understanding of multiple religious identities is required and that considering a multidimensional approach to religion as an ingroup might be beneficial.

In addition to religiosity enhancing prosocial behavior, our findings also revealed a significant effect of gender, with men (compared to women) showing greater charity and hospitality—regardless of the fundraiser's religiosity. This finding does not align with general prosociality studies, which consistently find women to be more prosocial than men (Einolf 2010; Mesch et al. 2011; Piper and Schnepf 2008). One possible explanation is that religiosity itself is context-dependent. While most studies reporting a gender gap in charitable behavior were conducted in a Western Christian context, our study was conducted in a Jewish context, where men, rather than women, tend to be more religious (Schnabel 2018). Similarly, a recent religious prosociality study in Iran (Mikani et al. 2022) reported a positive effect of men on prosociality in a Muslim context. Further exploration of the connection between religion, gender, and prosociality would be valuable, considering contextual elements such as religious affiliation and the gender of the target, especially given that our result could also be influenced by the gender of the fundraisers, who were both women.

This issue of understanding the dynamics between religiosity and prosociality connects to our third hypothesis, which posits religious community as a potential catalyst for enhancing prosociality. However, our analysis suggests that living within

a religiously homogeneous neighborhood does not necessarily foster more positive behavior—neither in general nor toward the religious ingroup. Specifically, we found that residing in such a neighborhood did not lead to greater prosocial behavior overall, not even in the form of increased “ingroup love” toward religious fundraisers, as evidenced by similar levels of donations and hospitality across neighborhoods. Instead, we observed a decline in prosociality in the form of “outgroup hostility”: Residents in these homogeneous neighborhoods were less likely to open their doors to secular, “outgroup” fundraisers. These findings raise important questions about the underlying drivers of prosocial behavior within religious groups, suggesting that community structure alone may not fully explain the complexities of religious prosocial behavior or ingroup bias, as some reviews have proposed (Galen 2012; Bloom 2012).

One possible explanation for the varied relationship between religious prosociality, ingroup favoritism, and the influence of religious communities can be found in self-categorization and social identity theories, particularly through the lens of religious priming. Self-categorization theory suggests that social identity is context-dependent, with certain aspects becoming dominant in specific situations (Turner and Reynolds 2012). Applied in social influence literature, this theory indicates that in uncertain situations, individuals emulate the behavior of ingroup members who share their social reality and norms. Social influence, therefore, can be seen as a form of self-influence, where individuals adopt behaviors they believe they would independently choose if fully informed (Flache et al. 2017).

Although religious “minimal prosociality” was not originally framed within self-categorization theory and priming, these concepts offer valuable insights into social influence within religious contexts. Primarily, religious priming has been shown to enhance prosocial behavior among believers (Shariff and Norenzayan 2007). Similarly, Malhotra (2010) found that religious individuals are more responsive to charity appeals on worship days, suggesting that religious environments effectively prime moral obligations. This may help explain why our findings show no significant increase in overall prosocial behavior within religiously homogeneous neighborhoods, yet indicate ingroup favoritism in response to direct requests from religious fundraisers in both neighborhoods. Religious ingroup favoritism may thus stem from the situational activation of religious identity in response to ingroup members, rather than from a generalized community effect. Consequently, religious neighborhoods alone may not consistently foster prosociality; specific contexts that prime religious identity are necessary to elicit prosocial responses. This distinction is further supported by our finding that religious fundraisers had no effect on secular participants. This aligns with the notion that religious priming minimally impacts nonreligious individuals, reinforcing that its effectiveness relies on pre-existing beliefs and norms (Shariff et al. 2016)

5 | Conclusions

It was established throughout the years that although religion has been positively associated with prosociality (Norenzayan and Shariff 2008; Park and Smith 2000), this is a “minimal prosociality” that is directed mainly toward other ingroup

members (Galen 2012; Preston and Ritter 2013; Saroglou 2005). Indeed, it seems that for religious people, “charity begins at home.” However, in a growing world of multidimensional religious identities (Ben-Nun Bloom et al. 2015; Schwadel et al. 2021; Wilkins-Laflamme 2014), it is not always clear what constitutes the religious “home.” Therefore, this study attempted to deepen the understanding of religious ingroup identification and prosocial behavior, studying whether secular individuals sharing religious affiliation count as an ingroup.

In conducting this study, we observed that religious individuals generally exhibit a higher propensity to donate than their secular counterparts. Furthermore, they demonstrate a tendency to donate more generously to those perceived as belonging to their religious ingroup, thus reinforcing the concept of ingroup favoritism within religious communities. However, our findings also suggest that the religious community’s structure alone is not the sole determinant of this behavior. From these insights, we derive two critical conclusions. First, our results challenge the notion of minimal prosociality by showing that even though religious individuals show favoritism toward their ingroup, they still tend to be more generous overall compared to secular individuals. Second, our study highlights the need for a deeper exploration into the underlying factors behind religious ingroup favoritism, especially concerning the intrinsic aspects of religiosity and its relation to religious priming. This emphasizes the necessity for more nuanced understandings in the study of religious prosocial behavior.

Finally, our study stands out for its innovative approach, employing a real-world field experiment with actual measurements of prosocial behaviors. This methodology allows us to directly observe and analyze the nuances of religious prosocial behavior in a natural setting, providing valuable insights that go beyond theoretical speculation or laboratory-based studies. The use of real donations and interactions adds a layer of authenticity to our findings, making them particularly relevant and applicable to understanding everyday prosocial dynamics within religious communities.

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Data Availability Statement

The data used in this study will be made available upon request.

Endnotes

¹ See <https://www.paamonim.org/en/> for more information.

² We conducted a semiopened individual pre-interview with 40 unrelated people (20 identified as religious, 16 seculars and 4 former-religious). Of 32 respondents who were familiar with the “Bells” organization, 19 affirmed that the organization has no religious affiliation, another 10 affirmed that it is neutral. Only 2 out of the 32 proclaimed that the organization has slight religious affiliation.

³In Israel one of the classifications of schools is made by the type of supervision: (1) State-secular education includes nonreligious schools that are under the supervision of the ministry of education. (2) State-religious education includes schools that are Zionist religious in their curriculum and lifestyle and their staff (teachers, management, and supervision) are mainly religious. (3) Ultra-religious education schools that are part of the independent and biblical networks which have an exemption from the state supervision and curriculum.

⁴<https://www.jerusalem.muni.il/he/residents/community-in-jerusalem/neighborhoods/givatmordechai/>

⁵<https://www.jerusalem.muni.il/he/residents/community-in-jerusalem/neighborhoods/kiryatyovelnighborhood/>

⁶We established this in interviews with residents. Additional evidence can be found in the settlements of a few ultra-Orthodox schools (Yeshiva) in the last two decades.

⁷A possible explanation for the observed differences in occupancy levels between the two neighborhoods relates to employment patterns within religious families. While the employment rates in households across all religious levels are approximately 80%, the Israel Central Bureau of Statistics data (available in the website <https://www.cbs.gov.il/en>) shows notable variations in dual employment rates. In 2019, about 54.7% of secular households had both partners employed, compared to 42.6% in religious households and only 25.2% in ultra-Orthodox households. These disparities continued into 2022, with secular households maintaining a dual employment rate of 53.7%, religious at 41.1%, and ultra-Orthodox at 24.7%. This pattern suggests that the differences in household occupancy during our experiment hours could be influenced by the varying employment trends across these religious categories.

⁸We acknowledge that gender is not inherently dichotomous and may be self-identified differently by participants. However, the unique nature of our study required us to infer gender based on participants' outward presentation. We assume that gender identification corresponded to participants' chosen gender appearance and pronouns during the interaction. Our sample did not include any clear cases of nonbinary individuals.

⁹For a robustness test we also applied linear regressions for all the models. Almost all the robust models provided the same results as the ordered logistic regression and Poisson regression in terms of the predictors' significance.

¹⁰Similar to the donation results, when secular individuals approached by secular fundraisers serve as the reference group, no differences in hospitality levels are found between secular individuals approached by religious fundraisers and those approached by secular fundraisers, indicating no ingroup effect.

¹¹Robustness tests employing Poisson logistic regression confirmed the consistency of our findings, yielding results aligned with those obtained from our primary analyses.

¹²We believe this limitation primarily affects the hospitality measure rather than the donation levels, as the fundraisers adhered to a standardized protocol during all interactions. This protocol minimized potential behavioral variation, reducing the likelihood that awareness of the condition influenced donation amounts, thereby ensuring greater objectivity in the donation measure.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.